

Myth 2: Posting a preprint will prevent subsequent publication in a peer-reviewed journal

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Have you heard the claim: “*Posting a preprint will prevent subsequent publication in a peer-reviewed journal.*” 😞 This widespread fear—among early-career researchers—has deep historical roots, but it doesn’t reflect today’s reality.

In this episode of **the ASAPbio Myth Busting Series**, we explore how journal policies have evolved, examine evidence from large-scale studies, and highlight the benefits of preprinting. From rapid dissemination to community input to direct invitation from journals, preprints can expand your reach and strengthen your work.

🌟 **Bottom line:** Posting a preprint does *not* prevent later journal publication. In fact, it helps speed up discovery, broaden your audience, and make science more open!

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Camera 1-2

Welcome to the ASAPbio Myth Busting Series. Today, we tackle a common fear: “Posting a preprint will prevent subsequent publication in a peer-reviewed journal.”

This concern is widespread, especially among early-career researchers. Is it actually true? Let’s find out.

Camera 3

This myth stems from the Ingelfinger rule¹, named after Franz Ingelfinger, an editor-in-chief of The New England Journal of Medicine in the 1960s. He argued that a journal should not consider any work that had been previously published or made public. For decades, this discouraged researchers from sharing their work ahead of journal-organized peer review. But times have changed!

Camera 4

Most journals today accept submissions that have been posted as preprints. A 2020 study² of 171 major academic journals found that over 70% clearly indicate that they allow some form of preprints. Of note, preprint policies vary considerably between disciplines. Over 90% of all journals in the life & earth sciences allow preprints in some way.

In fact, many prominent publishers actively **encourage** preprinting, and some may even **require** it for publication. For example:

- Springer Nature states on its website³: “Springer Nature journals encourage posting of preprints of primary research manuscripts on preprint servers of the authors’ choice, authors’ or institutional websites, and open communications between researchers whether on community preprint servers or preprint commenting platforms.”
- eLife goes further⁴ and “only peer review submissions that are available as preprints.”

Camera 5

Policies are one thing. What about real-life outcomes? About 70% of preprints are eventually published as journal articles.^{5,6} This high conversion rate indicates that far from blocking journal

¹ Definition of “sole contribution.” 1969. N Engl J Med 281:676–677. doi:10.1056/NEJM196909182811208

² Klebel T, Reichmann S, Polka J, McDowell G, Penfold N, Hindle S, Ross-Hellauer T. 2020. Peer review and preprint policies are unclear at most major journals. PLoS One 15:e0239518. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0239518

³ Springer Nature. n.d. Preprint Sharing. <https://www.springer.com/gp/editorial-policies/preprint-sharing>

⁴ eLife. n.d. Editorial Process. https://elife-rp.msubmit.net/html/elife-rp_author_instructions.html#process

⁵ Abdill RJ, Adamowicz EM, Blekhman R. 2020. International authorship and collaboration across bioRxiv preprints. Elife 9. doi:10.7554/eLife.58496

⁶ Fraser N, Momeni F, Mayr P, Peters I. 2020. The relationship between bioRxiv preprints, citations and altmetrics. Quant Sci Stud 1–21. doi:10.1162/qss_a_00043

publications, preprints are usually the first step towards eventual publication.

Preprints can open new opportunities! For one, preprints **increase visibility**. By the time a paper is submitted, editors can already see how much interest and feedback it has generated. Editors actively monitor preprint servers. In fact, there are cases where authors have received invitations from editors to submit the paper to their journals.

For authors, especially early-career researchers, posting a preprint also offers major advantages:

- Your work is available months or even years before publication in a journal
- Comments from the community can help improve the manuscript before journal-organized peer review
- Lastly, there is evidence that papers first posted as preprints attract more citations after journal publication than those that weren't.^{5,7}

Preprints aren't a dead end—they're a launchpad.

Camera 6

Are there exceptions? Yes. A handful of journals—mostly in clinical medicine—still restrict preprints or have special rules. But these are the exception, not the rule.

Thus, it remains crucial for authors to perform due diligence. Research your target journal's policies. And if you do post a preprint prior to submission, remember to be transparent with editors and inform them about its existence. It can help link the preprint to the final published version and assist with plagiarism detection software.

Camera 7

The bottom line? Posting a preprint **does not** prevent subsequent publication in a peer-reviewed journal. In fact, it can speed up discovery, expand your audience, and help make science more open!

Camera 8

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⁷ Colavizza G, Cadwallader L, Hrynaszkiewicz I. 2025. An analysis of the effects of open science indicators on citations in the French Open Science Monitor. arXiv [csDL].